

MODERN MINIMALLY INVASIVE APPROACHES IN THE SURGICAL TREATMENT OF ACUTE CHOLECYSTITIS

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Abstract. Gallstone disease remains one of the leading conditions in surgical practice. The study included the results of surgical treatment in 138 patients with acute cholecystitis. All surgical procedures and clinical and diagnostic observations were performed at the Department of General Surgery of the Kashkadarya Regional Multidisciplinary Medical Center during the period from 2022 to 2025. The patients' ages ranged from 18 to 89 years, with females predominating (84.8%). The diagnosis of acute cholecystitis was established based on clinical presentation, laboratory findings, and instrumental examination data. Laparoscopic cholecystectomy was performed in 25 patients (65.8%) with mild disease (Grade I) and in 13 patients (17.3%) with moderate severity (Grade II). In all cases, intraoperative findings included an enlarged and tense gallbladder, often associated with adhesions to the greater omentum or adjacent organs. In 31.6% of cases, gallbladder puncture with evacuation of 30–50 ml of bile was required. Intraoperative signs of acute obstructive cholecystitis were identified in 47.4% of patients, while phlegmonous cholecystitis with destructive changes of the gallbladder wall was observed in 21% of cases. Standard cholecystectomy was performed in 36 patients, whereas laparoscopic cholecystectomy with choledochal drainage according to Vishnevsky was carried out in 2 patients. The results obtained demonstrate that laparoscopic cholecystectomy is a reliable, safe, and cost-effective method for the surgical treatment of acute cholecystitis. We believe that with a cautious and individualized approach, the use of minimally invasive techniques provides optimal clinical outcomes and reduces the risk of postoperative complications.

Keywords: gallstone disease, acute calculous cholecystitis, laparoscopic cholecystectomy, choledochal drainage, rehabilitation.

Relevance. Gallstone disease (GSD) remains one of the leading causes of surgical pathology of the abdominal organs. Despite advances in diagnostic and

therapeutic approaches, the management of patients with GSD and its complicated forms continues to be a significant challenge in abdominal surgery due to the increasing incidence and complication rates. Acute calculous cholecystitis is diagnosed in 8–13.4% of patients admitted to surgical hospitals and predominantly affects elderly and senile individuals [2, 4]. In younger patients, gallstone disease is usually asymptomatic, with biliary colic occurring in only 1–4% of cases. In the absence of timely treatment, acute obstructive cholecystitis develops in approximately 20% of patients. Rapid progression of inflammation may lead to phlegmon, gangrene, or gallbladder perforation, significantly increasing mortality risk, especially in elderly patients, where destructive forms occur much more frequently [3]. Reduction of postoperative mortality and complications largely depends on early diagnosis, accurate interpretation of clinical and instrumental findings, and the rational choice of surgical strategy, including optimal timing and extent of intervention [1, 5, 6]. Currently, laparoscopic cholecystectomy, mini-access cholecystectomy, and open cholecystectomy are used in clinical practice. Among these, laparoscopic cholecystectomy is considered the gold standard due to its minimal invasiveness, lower complication rates, shorter hospital stay, and faster recovery.

Materials and Methods. The study analyzed the results of surgical treatment in 138 patients with acute cholecystitis treated at the Department of General Surgery of the Kashkadarya Regional Multidisciplinary Medical Center between 2022 and 2025. Patients ranged in age from 18 to 89 years (mean age 58.7 years). Females predominated (117 patients, 84.8%), while males accounted for 21 patients (15.2%). Diagnosis was established according to the Tokyo Guidelines, with mandatory assessment of disease severity. Surgical risk was evaluated using the APACHE II scoring system; a score ≥ 7 indicated high operative risk and guided treatment strategy. Diagnosis was based on clinical signs (right upper quadrant pain, positive Murphy's sign, fever), laboratory findings (leukocytosis, elevated C-reactive protein), and imaging features. Ultrasound was performed in all patients as the primary imaging modality. Computed tomography was used in 25 patients (18.1%) with severe or atypical presentation, and MR cholangiography was performed in 12 patients (8.7%) when choledocholithiasis was suspected. Histopathological examination revealed acute cholecystitis in 56.5%, gangrenous cholecystitis in 24.6%, and exacerbation of chronic cholecystitis in 18.9% of cases. Patients were divided into three groups according to the surgical approach.

Results. Laparoscopic cholecystectomy was performed in patients with mild (Grade I) and moderate (Grade II) disease, mainly within the first 24 hours after admission. The mean duration of laparoscopic surgery was 46.5 minutes. Intraoperatively, an enlarged and tense gallbladder was observed in all cases; gallbladder puncture was required in 31.6% of patients. Signs of obstructive cholecystitis were detected in 47.4%, and phlegmonous-destructive changes in 21% of cases. Mini-laparotomic cholecystectomy was mainly used in patients with moderate disease severity, with a mean access length of 5.5 ± 0.1 cm and an average operation time of 63.8 ± 2.2 minutes. Conventional laparotomy was reserved for patients with severe disease (Grade III) and pronounced inflammatory changes.

Discussion. The results confirm the safety and effectiveness of laparoscopic cholecystectomy in acute calculous cholecystitis when performed in a timely manner. The mini-laparotomic approach also demonstrated high efficacy, including in purulent-destructive forms, with favorable immediate outcomes and a low complication rate.

Conclusions. Laparoscopic cholecystectomy is a reliable, safe, and cost-effective method for treating acute cholecystitis. Mini-laparotomic cholecystectomy is an effective minimally invasive alternative for various forms of acute cholecystitis, including gangrenous and phlegmonous types. A differentiated approach to surgical technique selection reduces complication rates, mortality, and rehabilitation time.

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